

One dimensional coordination polymer of cadmium(II) with thiocyanate bridge : synthesis, characterization and molecular properties

Abhijit Pal^a, Merry Mitra^a, Bhaskar Biswas^a, Siang-Hua Huang^b, Hui-Lien Tsai^b and Rajarshi Ghosh^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : chem_rghosh@buruniv.ac.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 701, Taiwan, ROC

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Abstract : A one dimensional (1D) coordination polymer [Cd(bzpy)(NCS)(SCN)]_n (**1**) is synthesized and X-ray crystallographically characterized. **1** crystallizes in P-1 space group and the asymmetric unit contains one crystallographically independent cadmium(II) centre, one ligand (bzpy) and four thiocyanate ions. Cadmium(II) is surrounded by one nitrogen and one oxygen atom from the benzoyl pyridine moiety. Cadmium(II) here lies in a distorted octahedral environment with the CdN₃S₂O chromophore. Thermogravimetry reveals that **1** is thermally stable up to about 130 °C. After excitation at 350 nm, it gives strong emission in dimethylformamide (DMF) at 417 nm with a hump at 545 nm due to π-π* transition.

Keywords : Cadmium(II), thiocyanate, coordination polymer, thermogravimetry, fluorescence.

Introduction

Exploration of metal-organic coordination polymers with novel molecular architectures and special applications as catalysts, adsorbents, sensors, molecular magnetic and optical materials, has been the focus of recent investigations in solid-state chemistry^{1,2}. The crystal engineering of coordination polymers are generally achieved by the intrinsic geometric preferences of the metal centres and the various coordination modes of bridging linkers³. Various pseudohalides like azide⁴, thiocyanate⁵, cyanide⁶, etc. are common inorganic bridges to build up such polymers. Among the pseudohalides, thiocyanate is very much useful because of its flexidentate nature. Use of bivalent cadmium to synthesize coordination polymers, despite its toxic effects⁷, are frequent⁸ as it provides variety of coordination numbers. Strategic use of different weak interactions⁹ like hydrogen bonding, π...π interaction, C-H...π interaction, etc. along with the covalent/coordinate force¹⁰ generates different desired supramolecular architectures with interesting properties. In this endeavour, synthesis and crystallographic characterization of a one dimensional cadmium(II) coordination polymer [Cd(bzpy)(NCS)(SCN)]_n (**1**) [bzpy = 2-benzoyl pyridine], and its thermal stability and room temperature fluorescence behaviour are addressed.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The compound was synthesized from the cadmium(II) nitrate tetrahydrate and 2-benzoyl pyridine in methanol-acetonitrile reaction mixture. Ammonium thiocyanate was then added to this mixture and the whole reaction solution was kept for slow evaporation for a week to get colourless crystals of **1**. The compound is not soluble in common organic solvents. It dissolves in dimethyl formamide only.

Spectroscopic studies :

Infrared studies of **1** show that a peak at 1628 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the carbonyl group in the compound appears¹¹. Peak at 2116 cm⁻¹ appears as indicator band for the thiocyanate¹¹.

Room temperature fluorescence study of the title complex in DMF reveals that it gives strong emission (Fig. 1) at 417 nm with a hump at 545 nm after exciting the molecule at 350 nm. From the emission study of standard 2-benzoyl pyridine in DMF at 414 nm, it is concluded that the origin of emission in **1** is completely ligand centred and it is because of π-π* transition.

Thermal analysis :

The thermal behaviour (Fig. 2) of the complex **1** was followed up to 735 °C in a static nitrogen atmosphere

Fig. 1. Emission spectrum of 1 in DMF solution at room temperature.

Fig. 2. Thermal behaviour of 1.

with a heating rate of 10 °C per minute. 1 decomposes in two steps (Fig. 3). The first step between 128.15 and 323.08 °C corresponds to the endothermic process with the loss of the benzoyl pyridine and one thiocyanate group with the mass loss of 70.930% (calcd. 63.535%). The release of the nitrogen atom from the remaining intermediate species $[Cd(NCS)]^{1+}$ with the formation of a compound of unknown composition takes place in the second step (323.08–593.50 °C). The experimental mass loss

8.395% agrees well with the calculated mass loss 8.235%.

Crystal structure :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction of the compound provides the proper disposition of coordinating atoms to the cadmium centre. The thermal ellipsoid plot of the compound is given in Fig. 3. 1 crystallizes in P-1 space group and the asymmetric unit contains one crystallographically independent cadmium(II) centre, one ligand (bzpy) and four thiocyanate ions. Cadmium(I) is surrounded by one

Fig. 3. ORTEP representation of 1 with 20% thermal ellipsoid probability.

nitrogen and one oxygen atom from the benzoyl pyridine moiety. Two nitrogens (N2 and N3) and two sulphur atoms (S1 and S2) are from the thiocyanate. Cadmium(I) here lies in a distorted octahedral environment with the CdN_3S_2O chromophore. In the octahedron, from the bond angle and bond distance values (Table 1), one nitrogen (N2) and one sulphur (S1) from the thiocyanate are supposed to be in the axial position. The rest nitrogen atoms (N1, N3), oxygen (O1) and the sulphur atom (S2) are in equatorial position. The Cd-N and Cd-S distances are in the ranges 2.252(4)–2.378(3) Å and 2.6148(12)–2.7305(12) Å, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for 1

Bond distances		Bond angles	
N1-Cd1	2.378(3)	N3-Cd1-N2	92.03(14)
N2-Cd1	2.314(4)	N3-Cd1-N1	91.19(13)
N3-Cd1	2.252(4)	N2-Cd1-N1	89.13(11)
O1-Cd1	2.423(3)	N3-Cd1-O1	159.53(13)
S1-Cd1	2.7305(12)	N2-Cd1-O1	86.23(12)
S2-Cd1	2.6148(12)	N1-Cd1-O1	68.41(10)
		N3-Cd1-S2	105.56(12)
		N2-Cd1-S2	94.16(9)
		N1-Cd1-S2	162.77(9)
		O1-Cd1-S2	94.90(8)
		N3-Cd1-S1	95.12(10)
		N2-Cd1-S1	170.70(10)
		N1-Cd1-S1	84.78(8)
		O1-Cd1-S1	84.99(8)
		S2-Cd1-S1	89.65(4)

The 1D polymer was further stabilized by the $\pi \cdots \pi$ and C-H \cdots S interactions along *c* axis in solid-state (Tables 2 and 3, Fig. 4). The Cd-N and Cd-S bond lengths lie within a close range of 2.252(4)–2.314(4) Å and 2.6148(12)–2.7305(12) Å respectively (Table 1).

Table 2. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for 1

D-H \cdots A	D-H	H \cdots A	D \cdots A	D-H \cdots A
C10-H10 \cdots S1	0.93	2.86	3.591(5)	136

Table 3. $\pi \cdots \pi$ Interactions (Å, °) for 1

Cg-Cg	Cg-Cg distance	Dihedral angle (<i>i,j</i>)	Perpendicular distances between baricentres (<i>i,j</i>)
Cg3 \cdots Cg3 ^a	3.675(3)	0	3.4198(18)

Symmetry code : a = 2-x, 1-y, 2-z.

Conclusion :

Using self-assembly a one dimensional coordination polymer of cadmium(II) thiocyanate in combination with a heterocyclic aldehyde as end-capping ligand has been isolated and X-ray structurally characterized. The polymer is thermally stable and is an example of a luminous material.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoyl pyridine (Fluka, Germany), ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India), cadmium(II)

Fig. 4. Cooperative $\pi\cdots\pi$ and C-H \cdots S interaction in **1** affording 1D superstructure along *c*-axis.

nitrate hexahydrate (E. Merck, India) were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Thermal behaviour was investigated with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer with samples heated from 30–800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under nitrogen. UV-Vis spectrum was recorded with a Jasco model V-570 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of $[\text{Cd}(\text{bzpy})(\text{NCS})(\text{SCN})]_n$ (**1**) :

2-Benzoyl pyridine (0.183 g, 1 mmol) was added to a solution of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.308 g, 1 mmol) in 20 ml methanol/water mixture. Addition of NH_4NCS (0.152 g, 2 mmol) in portions was then done in the reaction mixture with constant stirring. Finally, the solution was filtered and the supernatant liquid was kept in open air for slow evaporation. After about a week or so colourless crystals of **1** were found. After a few days colourless crystals of **1** suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained that were collected by filtration, washed with hexane and

dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.288 g (70%) (Found : C, 44.00; H, 2.42; N, 12.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2\text{Cd}$ (**1**) : C, 44.29; H, 2.38; N, 11.06%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1628 (ν_{CO}), 2116 (ν_{NCS}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : 350, 479.

X-Ray crystallography :

The single crystal of **1** was mounted on the tip of a glass fiber with dimensions of 0.32 \times 0.30 \times 0.28 mm. Intensity data were collected at 296(2) K within the limits of $2.05^{\circ} < \theta < 28.35^{\circ}$ for **1** using a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD diffractometer equipped with graphite monochromatized Mo $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Systematically absent reflections led to the identification of space group P-1 for **1**. Of the 9056 total reflections for the complex, 3817 with ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) were used for structure solutions. The structures were solved by direct methods, and refined by the full-matrix least-squares method on F^2 values using the SHELX-97¹² program package. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically, whereas the hydrogen atoms were placed in ideal, calculated positions, with isotropic thermal parameters riding on their respective carbon atoms. The final differences Fourier map showed the maximum and minimum peak heights at -0.879 and $+1.373 \text{ e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$ for **1** with no chemical significance. Experimental details for X-ray data collection and the refinements of **1** are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1**

Formula	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2\text{Cd}$
Formula weight	411.79
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
<i>a</i> (\AA)	8.764(2)
<i>b</i> (\AA)	9.336(2)
<i>c</i> (\AA)	10.409(3)
α°	85.661(4)
β°	72.206(3)
γ°	73.468(3)
<i>V</i> (\AA^3)	777.4(3)
λ (\AA)	0.71073
ρ_{calcd} (g cm^{-3})	1.759
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>T</i> (K)	296(2)
μ (mm^{-1})	1.693
<i>F</i> (000)	404
Crystal size (mm^3)	0.321 \times 0.301 \times 0.275

Table-4 (contd.)

θ ranges ($^{\circ}$)	2.05 to 28.35
$h/k/l$	-11,11/-12,12/-13,13
Reflections collected	9056
Independent reflections	3817
T_{\max} and T_{\min}	0.631 and 0.590
Data/restraints/parameters	3817/0/190
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.084
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0359$ and $wR2 = 0.1005$
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0409$ and $wR2 = 0.1039$
Largest peak and hole ($e\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	-0.879 and +1.373
$R1 = \Sigma F_o - F_c /\Sigma F_o $, $wR2 = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2/\Sigma w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, $\text{calcd. } w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0463P)^2 + 0.8942P]$; where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Supplementary data :

CCDC 879370 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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